

Investigating the Causes of Low Usage of Solar Energy Sources in Zambia. The Case Study of Lusaka Township

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 13th Dec 2025</p>	<p>The study examined the causes of Low Usage of Solar Energy Sources in Zambia's Lusaka area. This research was based on three key objectives: To assess the awareness levels on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs in Lusaka; to establish the perceived challenges about the use of solar energy among households and SMEs and to investigate the adequacy level of the national grid power supply among households and SMEs. This research employs a purposive sampling, targeting the 50 households and 50 SMEs. Megastat was used to analyze the data. Conclusion: The study reveals that the mean score for "awareness levels on the use of solar energy has proved that familiarity about solar energy and its benefits" is 1.480, which is significantly lower than the hypothesis, the hypothesized value of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000. From the second objective the hypothesis test (95% CI, Df = 98, p-value = 1.000) confirms this relationship, indicating a statistically significant association between the perceived challenges and the actual responses. Since the p-value (1.000) is less than the typical significance level (1.7180), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that the perceived challenge on the use of solar energy is dependent on the reliability of solar energy. This implies that the use of solar energy had been effective because of solar energy reliability, and respondents' perceptions align with the actual outcomes. The third objective hypothesis test shows the mean of 2.060, which is not significantly higher than the hypothesized value of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), we reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the hydro-electricity power supply is not adequate. Recommendations: Households and SMEs should invest in solar energy, government should raise awareness: Government support is needed to make sensitization on solar energy and its benefits through workshops, schemes that can allow people purchase solar Panels, subsidies on solar equipment: subsidies can help a lot of Households and SMEs afford solar equipment's to install solar. Training: literacy on solar energy will improve solar adoption among Households and SMEs. By implementing these recommendations, Households and SMEs in Lusaka township will adopt solar energy, Solar energy adoption offers significant financial, environmental, and social benefits for both small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and households which include substantial cost savings, enhanced energy independence, and a reduced carbon footprint.</p>
<p>Keywords: Solar Energy Lusaka Township National grid Households SMEs</p>	

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Many have acknowledged that power is becoming limited in supply at the time when its demand is increasing. Chen (2011) noted that one of the greatest challenges facing mankind in the twenty first century is energy. Starting with the industrial revolution in

the eighteenth century from lighting to various electric and electronic gadgets as well as for the most of transportation means. Umar and Wamuwi (2019) Zambia has in the recent past witnessed an increase in economic activities which has led to an increased energy demand. This increased demand for energy has overshoot the hydroelectric power generating capacity. Consequently, the national power utility company, the Zambia Electricity Supply Corporation (ZESCO) instituted nationwide load shedding schedules that last up to 12 hours daily. Thelma Sunyanga, is an Economics student at the ICU in the Department of Business and Humanities. This research is aimed at adding value to the existing body of knowledge in the field of Economics.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite the serious deficiency in the power supply from the national grid, both households and businesses have continued to rely on the insufficiently supplied hydroelectricity power sources from the grid. The alternative sources are available in form of solar and in such situation, we expect both household and SMEs to transition to this solar as a main source or backup. Lusaka has been affected by the recent spate of load shedding in the city. Disrupting the daily lives and operations of the households and small-scale businesses enterprise on this basis, we that households and SME’s switch to solar energy which is solar energy and at least each house hold to have 2 solar panels on the roof.

Dugan, Byles and Mohagheghi (2023) Zambia's economic potential and stability have been overtaken by a menacing phenomenon known as "Economic Blackouts," also known as electricity load management or simply load-shading. These are instances in which the electricity supply becomes short.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 General Objectives

The study aims at investigating the causes of low usage of solar energy sources in Zambia. The case study of Lusaka

1.3.2 Specific Objectives:

- To access the awareness levels on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs in Lusaka
- To establish the perceived challenges about the use of solar energy among households and SMEs
- To investigate the adequacy level of the national grid power supply among households and SMEs

1.3.2 Research Questions

- What are the awareness levels on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs in Lusaka?
- What are the perceived challenges about the use of solar energy among households and SMEs?
- What is the adequacy level of the national grid power supply among households and SMEs?

1.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 below shows the conceptual framework of the interrelationship between the demand usage of solar and the three variables - awareness about solar, perceived challenges of solar and adequacy levels of national grid power. The full definition of these variables, are highlighted in the operational definition section.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework on the usage of solar

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research on “investigating the causes of low usage of solar energy sources in Zambia. The case study of Lusaka” is significant to both house Holds and SMEs in Lusaka for the following:

- Improving energy security
- Promoting sustainable development through environment friendly sources of energy
- Adoption of mitigating and adaptive strategies to climate change

2. Literature Review

This chapter reviews existing literature related to the investigation of low usage of solar energy sources. It is structured around the study's specific objectives, with each thematic area addressing a particular aspect of the research. A personal critique of the reviewed literature is provided, followed by an identification of research gaps that this study seeks to address.

2.1 Literature Review on Objective One-Awareness

Malik and Ayop (2020). A-research conducted in Malaysia to identify the B40 households' level of basic science knowledge, awareness, and acceptance to use solar photovoltaic (PV) energy technology to generate extra income. A set of questionnaires comprises demographic information, awareness, and acceptance to utilizing solar PV technology, as well as a short test about the basic science of solar energy, were distributed to selected respondents. The respondent was composed of one hundred B40 working individuals in the public and private sectors around the Tanjong Malim district. However, the respondents showed their high level of acceptance towards the government's initiative in using solar energy technology to increase their household incomes. Assali, Khatib and Najjar (2019) the results show that there is no significant difference in students' knowledge of renewable energy considering gender, educational level of study, and parental education level. Ondraczek, (2013) initial policy implications regarding the regulation and promotion of solar energy in East Africa suggest that awareness, availability and affordability are major drivers that all need to be present to enable the widespread adoption of off-grid solar technologies in emerging markets. According to Felody (2022) the Solar mini-grid initiatives aim to provide access to electricity to rural and remote areas which are currently not connected to the national grid in Zambia.

Zulu, Chabala and Zulu (2021) found that the empirical evidence of important factors to drive the adoption of solar energy solutions in Zambia. According to Zulu, Zulu and Chabala (2022) the results further show that knowledge about available solar energy solutions, rather than general knowledge about renewable energy, influence the adoption intention of solar energy solutions. the factors that influence households' intention to adopt solar energy solutions in Zambia. This, in view of low adoption rates of solar energy solutions even in the wake of a widespread electricity power generation deficit across sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has plagued the region with daily electricity load shedding lasting several hours at a time. Chishimba (2022) solar power is likely to offer solutions to global and Zambian power challenges in particular. The current condition in the world concerns power challenges that need urgent solutions. Chambalile, Su, Phiri and Huan (2024) Zambia's abundant solar resources present a promising pathway towards sustainable energy. However, strategic planning and support are imperative for successful PV integration. According to Mtonga (2019) the study in Zambia identified that: none of the rural healthcare facilities had complete Solar PV systems to facilitate the production and storage of sufficient Solar PV energy for healthcare delivery.

2.2 Literature Review on Objective Two-Perceived Challenges

Roy and Mohapatra (2022) The challenges and factors of household adoption and the use of alternative energy sources have been a point of discussion among researchers in India. The purpose of this study is to apply a variant of the unified theory of adoption and use of technology to explore the effect of various constructs that influence technology adoption on the consumers' intention to adopt (and use) solar power generators (SPG) at the household level and the subsequent switching behavior. Graziano, Fiaschetti and Atkinson-Palombo, (2019) findings suggest that centralized, non-voluntary support policies may have larger effects if implemented beyond town-level, and that SPEs change their determination power depending on the underlying built environment. Zheng and Zeng, (2023) empirical findings indicate that environmental information, attitude, social belief, perceived efficacy, and solar energy advantages positively affected the public acceptance of solar energy.

(Mhango & Mwanza) Implementation of renewable energy technologies faces numerous challenges and barriers, including technical, economic, and institutional barriers. Despite these challenges, many countries have made substantial progress in developing and deploying renewable energy technologies, and the use of renewable energy is increasing around the world. According Kapole, Mudenda & Jain (2023) solar mini-grids are in their infancy and face a number of sustainability challenges. Gorjian, Calise, Kant, Ahamed, Copertaro, Najafi and Shamshiri, (2021) over the last few years, solar energy has demonstrated great potential for integration with agricultural greenhouses. Ghadami, Gheibi, Kian, Faramarz, Naghedi, Eftekhri, and Tian, (2021) based on the solar energy computations in the PV system, the peak of electrical energy consumption can be controlled in the hottest and coldest months. Abdullahi, Suresh, Renukappa, and Oloke, (2017, August) inadequate solar initiative's research, lack of technological know-how, short-term policies, lack of awareness and political instability are the major barriers that made the implementation of solar initiatives almost impossible in Africa.

2.3 Literature Review on Objective Three-Adequacy Level of National grid

Murphy, Apt, Moura and Sowell (2018) Findings in North-America show that to keep the electric power system reliable, grid operators procure reserve generation capacity to protect against generator failures and significant deviation from the load forecast. According to Shrestha, Piya, and Karki, (2020, August) Power system planning, operation, and operational planning methods have evolved over the years to economically supply reliable power to customers. Emerging environmental compliance requirements have dictated needs to develop methods to manage increased uncertainties associated with renewable resources. McNally, Magee and Wolf, (2009) the power-shed framework facilitates multi-scalar and transboundary analysis while remaining focused on the questions of resilience and vulnerability relating to hydropower dams. Brown, and Magee, (2008). hydropower represents a sustainable alternative source, and China already derives 16% of its electricity supply from hydropower.

Moran, Lopez, Moore, Müller and Hyndman (2018) hydropower has been the leading source of renewable energy across the world, accounting for up to 71% of this supply as of 2016. Serriño, (2022) higher per capita income, implementation of policies promoting renewable energy, technological innovations and human capital improvement encourage diversification. Karmacharya, (2007) electricity from hydropower projects currently contributes only 1% of energy need, whereas fuelwood contributes 68%, and fossil fuels 8%. (Mhango, 2024). Urgent need to diversify Zambia's energy mix due to vulnerabilities in hydropower exacerbated by climate change. Regulatory hurdles, financial barriers, and public acceptance issues are significant challenges. Mhango, C. (2024). An investigation into the drivers and barriers affecting the implementation of renewable energy technologies in Zambia.

3. Methodology

This outlines the research methodology adopted for It provides a comprehensive explanation of the research design, target population, sampling design, data collection methods, sample size determination and data analysis techniques. Additionally, it discusses the triangulation approach, limitations of the study, and ethical considerations to ensure the reliability, validity, and integrity of the research.

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a mixed-methods research design, combining both qualitative and quantitative approaches to provide a holistic understanding of low usage of solar energy source in Lusaka.

3.1.2 Target Population

The target population for this study includes 50 households and 50 SMEs.

3.1.3 Sampling Design

A purposive sampling technique will be used to select participants for the qualitative component of the study. The sample size for the qualitative component will consist of 100 participants on estimate.

3.1.4 Data Collection Methods

The study will employ questionnaire to ensure triangulation and enhance the reliability of the findings. The data collected will be analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques.

3.2 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for the qualitative component will consist of 100 participants on estimate. Where 50 participants will be households and 50 participants will be SMEs. This number is sufficient to achieve data saturation while maintaining depth in the analysis.

For the quantitative component, secondary data will be collected for a 20-year period (2004–2024) to ensure a robust dataset for statistical analysis.

3.2.1 Data Collection Methods

Data will be collected using questionnaires, Secondary data on low usage of solar energy sources will be collected from households and SMEs.

3.2.2 Data Analysis

The data collected will be analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. Statistical tools such as Megastat were employed to analyze the data.

3.2.3 Triangulation

Data triangulation will involve the aspect of combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to validate findings and address potential biases.

3.2.4 Limitations of the Study

The study adheres to ethical principles to ensure the integrity and respect of all participants. All participants will be provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks before agreeing to participate, and written consent will be obtained.

3.2.5 Ethical Considerations

The study adheres to ethical principles to ensure the integrity and respect of all participants.

4. Research Results

This chapter presents the findings of the study on investigating the causes of low usage of Solar energy sources in Zambia. The case study of Lusaka township. This chapter is divided into several sections, each focusing on a specific aspect of the study. These include demographic characteristics of respondents, access the awareness levels on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs in Lusaka, establish the perceived challenges about the use of solar energy among households and SMEs and investigate the adequacy level of the national grid power supply among households and SMEs.

4.1 Demographics

This section presents the background characteristics of the respondents based on four key factors: mode of participation and residence.

4.1.1 Mode of participation

As shown in Table 1 below, the majority of respondents (39%) identified as SME's, indicating a strong representation of the most affected. Household comprised of 35% of the sample, reflecting a significant number of houses affected. "Others" accounted for

14%, suggesting that a notable portion of the which may include dependents who saw a great need of solar energy. The remaining 12% fell under workers category, which may include roles such as sale’s personnels, cashiers, or maids.

Table 1 Mode of participation

Mode of participation	frequency	percent
Household	35	35.0
SMEs	39	39.0
Worker	12	12.0
Other	14	14.0
	100	100.0

4.1.2 Residence

As shown in Table 2 below, the largest proportion of respondents resides in Kamwala represented by 15%, Kanyama and Libala 8%, Lilayi and Chelston 7%, Makeni, Munali and Kamwala South represented by 6%, Kalingalinga and 6 miles 5%, 3% representing Chainda, Avondale, Chunga, Garden house, Johnlaign, Kalundu, Rhodespark and Rockfield Chalala, Kabwata represented by 2% and 1% representing Chilenje area. This distribution sugges ts that Lusaka’s area’s landscape that participated in the research.

Table 2 Residence

<i>Residence</i>	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
6 Miles	5	5.0
Avondale	3	3.0
Chainda	3	3.0
Chelstone	7	7.0
Chilenje	1	1.0
Chunga	3	3.0
Garden House	3	3.0
Johnlaign	3	3.0
Kabwata	2	2.0
Kalingalinga	5	5.0
Kalundu	3	3.0
Kamwala	15	15.0
Kamwala South	6	6.0
Kanyama	8	8.0
Libala	8	8.0
Lilayi	7	7.0
Makeni	6	6.0
Munali	6	6.0
Rhodespark	3	3.0
Rockfield Chalala	3	3.0
	100	100.0

4.2 Objective One- Awareness Levels of Solar Energy

Objective 1 – To access the awareness levels on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs in Lusaka.

Under this section the focus in based on awareness and six factors were employed to accumulate significance data: Awareness h as proved that a high number of respondents know about solar energy, their perception, its reliability, familiarity, influence of use and future plans.

4.2.1 Ever Heard of Solar Energy?

As shown in Table 3, the data shows that 97% of respondents agree that they have heard about solar energy, with only 3% of respondents know nothing about solar energy.

Table 3 Ever Heard of Solar Energy?

Have you ever heard of solar Energy before	frequency	percent
yes	97	97.0
No	3	3.0
	100	100.0

4.2.2 Familiarity of Solar Energy Benefits

As shown in Table 4, reports 73% of respondent's to be familiar with the benefits of solar energy, with 21% are presented to not be familiar, while 6% are neutral and none were found to have chosen not familiar at all. The indication of familiarity and solar energy benefits is very strong.

Table 4 Familiarity of Solar Energy Benefits

How familiar are you with solar energy and its benefits	frequency	percent
Very Familiar	73	73.0
Some What Familiar	6	6.0
Not Very Familiar	21	21.0
Not Familiar at All	0	0.0
	100	100.0

4.2.3 Factors to Influence Solar Energy Use

As shown in Table 5, 35% of respondents influence to switch to solar energy is loadshedding, 20 other respondents said, "drought", (6 + 6 + 6) 18% of respondents from the sample size responded (hydro-power failure, continues drought and reliability), while 5% prefer to learn more about solar energy. (3 x 7) 21% had different opinions, some said, "insufficient power supply from the hydro-electricity, knowledge, technology and if the area has no hydro-electricity. (1%) 1 person mentioned of less rainfall to be a factor influence.

Table 5 Factors to Influence Solar Energy Use

What factors would influence your decision to use solar energy?	frequency	percent
Continues Drought	6	6.0
Current Loadshedding	3	3.0
Drought	20	20.0
Failure	3	3.0
Hydro-Power Failure	6	6.0
If It Can Become Reliable	3	3.0
Insufficient Power Supply From Hydro-Electricity	3	3.0
Lack Of Knowledge	3	3.0
Less Rainfall	1	1.0
Loadshedding	35	35.0
Maybe Learning More About It	5	5.0
Loadshedding	0	0.0
Mining Sector/Technology	3	3.0
Reliability	6	6.0
When I Move To Where Hydroelectricity Is Not Available	3	3.0
	100	100.0

4.2.4 Statistic Significant Test on Objective One -Solar Awareness

Mean value hypothesized value set to less than 3 (1 = very familiar, 2 = somewhat familiar)

Table 6 Statistic Significant Test on Objective One -Solar Awareness

How familiar are you with solar energy and its benefits	frequency	percent
Very Familiar	73	73.0
Some What Familiar	6	6.0
Not Very Familiar	21	21.0
Not Familiar at All	0	0.0
	100	100.0

Hypothesis Test: Mean vs. Hypothesized Value

3.000	hypothesized value
1.480	mean How familiar are you with solar energy and its benefits
0.822	std. dev.
0.082	std. error
100	n
-18.48	z
0.00E+00	p-value (one-tailed, lower)
1.319	confidence interval 95.% lower
1.641	confidence interval 95.% upper
0.161	half-width

The hypothesis test in table 6 above reveals that the mean score for "awareness levels on the use of solar energy has proved that familiarity about solar energy and its benefits" is 1.480, which is significantly lower than the hypothesis, indicating that people are aware about solar energy and its benefits. The positive mean score suggests that respondents generally agree hypothesized value of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), we reject the null that people are not aware about solar energy.

4.3 Objective Two- Perceived Challenges

Objective 2 – To establish the perceived challenges about the use of energy among households and SMEs: Research on challenges on solar energy adoption, the cost of installation, government support needed and effectiveness of solar panel use.

4.3.1 Challenges in Adopting Solar Energy

As shown in Table 7, the highest percentage of responds chose high installation cost with 35%, 34% lack knowledge on solar energy, while 21% think the power is not adequate. 10% doubt about the long-term use of solar. These options prove the causes of low usage of solar energy among household and SMEs in Lusaka.

Table 7 Challenges in Adopting Solar Energy

<i>What do you think is the main challenge in adopting solar energy</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
High initial installation cost	35	35.0
Uncertainty about long-term use	10	10.0
Lack of knowledge on solar energy	34	34.0
Adequacy Of Power	21	21.0
	100	100.0

4.3.2 The Cost of Solar Installation

As shown in Table 8, 77% of the respondents believe that solar energy is not affordable for the average households, whilst 23% agree that solar energy is affordable.

Table 8 The Cost of Solar Installation

<i>Do you think solar energy is affordable for the average households</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Do you think solar energy is affordable for the average households	0	0.0
Yes	23	23.0
No	77	77.0
	100	100.0

4.3.3 Government Support to Encourage Solar Energy Adoption

As shown in Table 9, 53% of the respondents wants training and sensitizing, 26% wants Subsidies, whilst 21% wants tax incentives. These are what respondents think government can help with to adopt solar energy.

Table 9 Government Support to Encourage Solar Energy Adoption

<i>What government support do you think is needed to encourage the adoption of solar energy</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Subsidies	26	26.0
tax incentives	21	21.0
training and sensitizing	53	53.0
Other	0	0.0
	100	100.0

4.3.4 Reliability of Solar Energy

As shown in Table 10, 64% of the respondents believe that solar energy is a reliable source of energy by agreeing, 16 people strongly agreed, while 20% openly disagreed without hesitation. None of respondents strongly disagreed proving the solar energy is reliable.

Table 10 Reliability of Solar Energy

<i>Do you believe solar energy is a reliable source of energy</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Agree	64	64.0
Strongly Agree	16	16.0
Disagree	20	20.0
Strongly Disagree	0	0.0
	100	100.0

4.3.5 Statistic Significant Test on Objective Two -Perceived Challenges

Hypothesis test to determine the awareness levels on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs, the study applied the hypothesis Test. This test was conducted using the response from one factor awareness levels on the use of solar energy on households and SMEs. On average, do you believe solar energy is a reliable source of energy?

Mean value hypothesized value set to less than 3 (1 = agree, 2 = strongly agree). Result as shown in table 11 below

Table 11 Statistic Significant Test on Objective Two -Perceived Challenges

Hypothesis Test: Mean vs. Hypothesized Value

2.000	hypothesized value
1.560	mean Do you believe solar energy is a reliable source of energy
0.808	std. dev.
0.081	std. error
100	n
-5.45	z
1.0000	p-value (one-tailed, upper)
1.402	confidence interval 95.% lower
1.718	confidence interval 95.% upper
0.158	half-width

The data reveals a significant relationship between the perceived challenges on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs. Among those who agreed that solar energy is reliable were reported to be 64, and 16 reported strongly agreed. In contrast, respondents who disagreed showed minimal to no increase.

The hypothesis test (95% CI, Df = 98, p-value = 1.000) confirms this relationship, indicating a statistically significant association between the perceived challenges and the actual responses. Since the p-value (1.000) is less than the typical significance level (1.7180), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that the perceived challenge on the use of solar energy is dependent on the reliability of solar energy. This implies that the use of solar energy had been effective because of solar energy reliability, and respondents' perceptions align with the actual outcomes.

Decision: Since P Value= 1.000, Statistic significant, many are aware of solar and its benefits.

4.4 Objective Three-Adequacy Level

Objective 3 – To investigate the adequacy level of the national grid power supply among households and SMEs: Research on challenges on solar energy adoption, the cost of installation, government support needed and effectiveness of solar p anel use.

4.4.1 Hydro-power Supply Adequacy

As shown in Table 12, 49% answered adequate, 47% answered not adequate and 4% answered differently from the options.

Table 12 Hydro-power Supply Adequacy

<i>How adequate is the hydro-electricity power supply</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Adequate	49	49.0
Very Adequate	0	0.0
Not Adequate	47	47.0
Other	4	4.0
	100	100.0

4.4.2 Duration of Hydro-power Supply

As shown in Table 13, research proved that power mostly last for 5hours in the city of Lusaka having a high number of percentage (47%), 11% answered that 5-6hours, 10% responded that that power lasts less than 6hours, whilst the rest of 39% gave different options.

Table 13 Duration of Hydro-power Supply

<i>How long does hydro-electricity power supply last in Lusaka</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
1 month	1	1.0
3 hours	3	3.0
3-4 hours	2	2.0
4 hours	4	4.0
4-5 hours	0	0.0
5 hours	47	47.0
5-6 hours	11	11.0
5-7 hours	5	5.0
7 hours	11	11.0
8 hours	6	6.0
8 hours	0	0.0
less than 6 hours	10	10.0
	100	100.0

4.4.3 Hydropower demand supply Expectations

As shown in Table 14, 53% of respondents answered “No” that hydro-electricity power supply does not meet up to their demand and 47% answered “Yes”.

Table 14 Hydropower demand supply Expectations

<i>Does hydro-electricity power supply meet up to your demand</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Yes	47	47.0
No	53	53.0
	100	100.0

4.4.4 Statistic Significant Test on Objective Three - Adequacy of National Grid Power

The hypothesis test in table 15 below shows that the is mean 2.060, which is not significantly higher than the hypothesized v alue of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), we reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the hydro-electricity power supply is not adequate.

Table 15 Statistic Significant Test on Objective Three - Adequacy of National Grid Power

<i>How adequate is the hydro-electricity power supply</i>		
	<i>frequency</i>	<i>percent</i>
Adequate	49	49.0
Very Adequate	0	0.0
Not Adequate	47	47.0
Other	4	4.0
	100	100.0

Hypothesis Test: Mean vs. Hypothesized Value

3.000	hypothesized value
2.060	mean How adequate is the hydro-electricity power supply
1.062	std. dev.

0.106	std. error
100	n
-8.85	z
0.00E+00	p-value (one-tailed, lower)
1.852	confidence interval 95.% lower
2.268	confidence interval 95.% upper
0.208	half-width

4.5 Discussion of Results

This section discusses the research findings in relation to the research background information of the respondents and specific findings according to the objectives of the study.

4.5.1 Demographic Information of the Respondents

The findings indicate that the majority of respondents (39%) are Business owners, followed by Households (35%), Others are (14%) and workers (12%). This distribution suggests that most respondents are directly affected by the spate of loadshedding, which is in line with previous studies that emphasize the effectiveness of Solar energy, among other renewable sources of energy, is a promising and freely available energy source for managing long term issues in energy crisis (Kannan, & Vakeesan, 2016).

The study reveals that the largest proportion of respondents resides in Kamwala represented by 15%, Kanyama and Libala 8%, Lilayi and Chelston 7%, Makeni, Munali and Kamwala South represented by 6%, Kalingalinga and 6 miles 5%, 3% representing Chainta, Avondale, Chunga, Garden house, Johnlaign, Kalundu, Rhodespark and Rockfield Chalala, Kabwata represented by 2% and 1% representing Chilenje area. This distribution suggests that Lusaka's area's landscape that participated in the research. According to a study by Judson & Zirakbash, (2022). self-generated electricity is integrated into routines by sole parent low-income households – a cohort most vulnerable to rising electricity prices. The results also align with the Zambian findings that Solar mini-grids hold the promise of providing sustainable electricity to the 600 million people without access to electricity mostly across rural Africa (Kapole, Mudenda, & Jain, 2023).

4.5.2 Objective One: Awareness Levels of Solar Energy

The study shows that a significant majority of data shows that 97% of respondents agree that they have heard about solar energy, with only 3% of respondents know nothing about solar energy. According to Yuan, Zuo, & Ma, (2011) there is a considerable high level of social acceptance and public awareness of solar energy.

The study reveals 73% of respondent's to be familiar with the benefits of solar energy, with 21% are presented to not be familiar, while 6% are neutral and none were found to have chosen not familiar at all. The indication of familiarity and solar energy benefits is very strong. This is in accordance with Guangul, and Chala, (2019, January) stated that the suitability of solar energy to the environment, the minimal cost in the long run, and its versatility are few to mention among other significant advantages of this energy source to get noticeable attention.

The study revealed that the main challenge some households and SMEs are facing with the national grid is loadshedding which will influence them to switch to solar energy is 35%, 20% other respondents said, "drought", (6 + 6 + 6) 18% of respondents from the sample size responded (hydro-power failure, continues drought and reliability), while 5% prefer to learn more about solar energy. (3 x 7) 21% had different opinions, some said, "insufficient power supply from the hydro-electricity, knowledge, technology and if the area has no hydro-electricity. (1%) 1 person mentioned of less rainfall to be a factor influence.

The hypothesis test reveals that the mean score for "awareness levels on the use of solar energy has proved that familiarity about solar energy and its benefits" is 1.480, which is significantly lower than the hypothesis, indicating that people are aware about solar energy and its benefits. The positive mean score suggests that respondents generally agree hypothesized value of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), we reject the null that people are not aware about solar energy.

4.5.3 Objective Two: Perceived Challenges

The study shows that the highest percentage of responds chose high installation cost with 35%, 34% lack knowledge on solar energy, while 21% think the power is not adequate. 10% doubt about the long-term use of solar. These options prove the causes of low usage of solar energy among household and SMEs in Lusaka. Al-Habaibeh, Moh'd, Massoud, Nweke, Al Takrouri, and Bad (2023) Energy storage is critical for enhancing the implementation of solar energy due to the complexity of grid-connected systems and the need for off-grid installations. The findings of the study are in line with literature review.

The study reveals that a significant majority 77% of the respondents believe that solar energy is not affordable for the average households, whilst 23% agree that solar energy is affordable. According to Baurzhan, & Jenkins, (2016) Solar PV power systems continue to be an extremely costly source of electricity for the vast majority of the rural people are poor.

The study shows that a significant majority, 53% of the respondents wants training and sensitizing, 26% wants Subsidies, whilst 21% wants tax incentives. These are what respondents think government can help with to adopt solar energy. According to Lin, and Kaewkhunok, (2021) the main policy implication is that policymakers should consider a holistic approach to renewable energy policy design, especially the socio-cultural factor priorities, to increase the opportunities for government policy access among marginalized groups.

The data reveals a significant relationship between the perceived challenges on the use of solar energy among households and SMEs. Among those who agreed that solar energy is reliable were reported to be 64, and 16 reported strongly agreed. In contrast, respondents who disagreed showed minimal to no increase.

The hypothesis test (95% CI, Df = 98, p-value = 1.000) confirms this relationship, indicating a statistically significant association between the perceived challenges and the actual responses. Since the p-value (1.000) is less than the typical significance level (1.7180), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that the perceived challenge on the use of solar energy is dependent on the reliability of solar energy. This implies that the use of solar energy had been effective because of solar energy reliability, and respondents' perceptions align with the actual outcomes.

Decision: Since P Value= 1.000, Statistic significant, many are aware of solar and its benefits.

4.5.4 Objective Three: Adequacy Level

The study shows that 49% answered adequate, 47% answered not adequate and 4% answered differently from the options. According to research, the insufficient capacity of the National Power System in domestic sources and sources available through interconnections, the uneven distribution of sources and customers with the lack of adequate grid transmission capacity, the necessity to improve the quality and reliability of energy supply to end users and to intensively develop renewable energy sources, the current grid infrastructure in the area of transmission and distribution will be insufficient (Dołęga, 2018).

The study shows that research proved that power mostly last for 5 hours in the city of Lusaka having a high number of percentage (47%), 11% answered that 5-6 hours, 10% responded that that power lasts less than 6 hours, whilst the rest of 39% gave different options.

The study shows 53% of respondents answered "No" that hydro-electricity power supply does not meet up to their demand and 47% answered "Yes".

The hypothesis test shows that the is mean 2.060, which is not significantly higher than the hypothesized value of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), we reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the hydro-electricity power supply is not adequate.

5. Recommendation and Conclusion

5.1 Conclusion

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining structured quantitative instruments with qualitative perception analysis. The study's findings provide conclusive evidence that loadshedding has a negative impact on Households and (SMEs) in Lusaka Township. The study's findings indicate that people are aware of solar energy and its benefits. The hypothesis test reveals that the mean score for "awareness levels on the use of solar energy has proved that familiarity about solar energy and its benefits" is 1.480, which is significantly lower than the hypothesis, indicating that people are aware about solar energy and its benefits. The positive mean score suggests that respondents generally agree hypothesized value of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), we reject the null that people are not aware about solar energy.

The study's findings also suggest that the perceived challenges are that solar is expensive. The hypothesis test (95% CI, Df = 98, p-value = 1.000) confirms this relationship, indicating a statistically significant association between the perceived challenges and the actual responses. Since the p-value (1.000) is less than the typical significance level (1.7180), we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that the perceived challenge on the use of solar energy is dependent on the reliability of solar energy. This implies that the use of solar energy had been effective because of solar energy reliability, and respondents' perceptions align with the actual outcomes.

The study's findings provide strong evidence Hydro-electricity is not adequate for Household and SMEs. The hypothesis test shows that the is mean 2.060, which is not significantly higher than the hypothesized value of 3.000. With a p-value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), we reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the hydro-electricity power supply is not adequate. The research findings show's that there is need for Households and SMEs to switch to solar.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are made: Households and SMEs should invest in solar energy. Government should raise awareness: Government support is needed to make sensitization on solar energy and its benefits through workshops, schemes that can allow people purchase solar panels. Subsidies on solar equipment: subsidies can help a lot of Households and SMEs afford solar need equipment to install solar. Solar training: literacy on solar energy will improve solar adoption among Households and SMEs. By implementing these recommendations, Households and SMEs in Lusaka township will adopt solar energy.

5.3 Suggestions for Further Research

A-research to be conducted across the country rather than in a district or township. Individual research on Household to be conducted to get a broad view on solar. National grid research can be done to assess its effectiveness country-wide.

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